

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY CLASSES

Mamadaminova Dilshoda Rustam qizi

Toyloq district, Samarkand region

English teacher of the 25th general secondary school

Abstract: *In this article, various methods and ways of teaching English to the younger generation from preschool and elementary grades are considered and studied. Teaching foreign languages to the young generation from their childhood has many advantages. One of the most important factors is that they love the language from childhood and arouse their interest in language learning.*

Key words: *secondary education schools, primary education, language skills, "Tree" method, "The fastest" method*

Currently, many methods and ways of teaching English to the young generation, which is the demand of the times, from preschool and elementary grades, are being developed, and many researches are being conducted on the issues of practical application. . The results of such research are sure to show their results. Teaching foreign languages to the young generation from their childhood has many advantages. One of the most important factors is that they love the language from childhood and arouse their interest in language learning. Because during the course of learning a foreign language, they get to know not only the language of that nation, but also the nationality, values and way of life of its

inhabitants. Concepts and impressions about the world begin to appear in the student's mind.

Knowing a language opens up many possibilities. It certainly has a positive effect on world travel, business, learning, and outlook. Foreign languages are taught step-by-step to schoolchildren, that is, elementary school students. In this process, the use of multimedia and oral teaching methods in a suitable way for the students of the 1st grade will have a good effect. English alphabet and writing skills are completely wrong for 1st graders without a full understanding and knowledge of their mother tongue. Therefore, the first lessons of English are taught through games, multimedia tools and oral methods, and then when the students move to the 2nd grade, the literacy period is completely completed for them, and that's why. from the period, it is necessary to teach them the English alphabet and writing skills and to establish the formation of students' knowledge. In this way, they can form and develop a foreign language. The English language, with its many aspects and interesting features, attracts the interest of the student and leads to serious study of this language.

Starting from the 2013-2014 academic year, continuous teaching of the English language in the form of game-style exercises and oral speech lessons was started in general secondary schools. From the 2nd grade, you can organize other educational games aimed at mastering grammar. For example, "Tree", "Dictionary", "Fastest" and many similar methods can be used.

If we talk about the "tree" method, this method is mainly taught to children in the form of a game. A beautiful picture of a tree is drawn on a large white paper (poster). Pupils are given questions about flowers, or they can also write questions

about fruits. Then, if the students answer the questions correctly, they glue that flower (fruit) to the tree. In this way, students make their own "tree of knowledge".

"Dictionary" - this method mainly focuses on comparison and comparison. That is, the students are divided into 2 groups, and the 1st group is given the task of translating words and text using the electronic dictionary, and the 2nd group is the first to translate the words and text. In this method, of course, group 1 quickly fulfills the condition. However, in the memory of the 2nd group, the words remain more and for a longer time. Because they find every word with difficulty and hard work. In this way, the groups share many useful and effective ways of using these two variants of dictionaries.

I will explain about the "fastest" method as follows. In this method, t-shirts are made from small pieces of paper and distributed to students. The students wrote down the words they knew on the paper. Whoever writes the most words and completes them first is the fastest reader. Using these and many similar methods and games, it is possible to ensure that children learn English well and perfectly. The results of these methods are clearly very beneficial.

In conclusion, it can be said that teaching foreign languages (English) to the young generation from the primary grades of schools has many advantages. And in this way we can develop their knowledge and skills. Based on the knowledge they have acquired in the primary classes, they will be able to learn English more deeply without difficulty when they move to the upper class, and they will have the opportunity to speak in this language. That is why it is necessary to inculcate in their minds that it is necessary to study languages carefully from a young age.

References:

1. Iriskulov A.T va boshqalar ; Kids' English pupil's book 2-sinf -Toshkent - O'zbekiston ; 2014
2. Passov Ye.I. Kommunikativniy metod obucheniya inoyazichnomu govoreniyu . M.: Prosveshenie , 1991
3. Xoshimov O'. Yoqubov I. Ingliz tili O'qitish metodikasi. T., -2003
4. Khakimov, S. R., & Sharopov, B. K. (2023). Educational Quality Improvement Events Based on Exhibition Materials in Practical Training Lessons. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education*, 1(2), 5-10.
5. Khamidov, A. I., & Khakimov, S. (2023). Study of the Properties of Concrete Based on Non-Fired Alkaline Binders. *European Journal of Geography, Regional Planning and Development*, 1(1), 33-39.
6. Khamidov, A., & Khakimov, S. (2023). MOISTURE LOSS FROM FRESHLY LAID CONCRETE DEPENDING ON THE TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY OF THE ENVIRONMENT. *Science and innovation*, 2(A4), 274-279.
7. Yuldashev, S. H., & Xakimov, S. (2022). ABOUT VIBRATION ARISING FROM RAILWAY TRANSPORT. *Science and Innovation*, 1(5), 376-379.
8. Rasuljon o'g'li, K. S., & Muhammadjanovna, K. F. (2023). ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING STEEL REINFORCEMENTS AND COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENTS IN BUILDING STRUCTURES. *AMALIY VA FUNDAMENTAL TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI | JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND FUNDAMENTAL RESEARCH*, 2(6), 1-5.

